

Studies on Physico-Chemical Properties of Emulsions Stabilised by Some Indian Medicinal Plant Gums

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Of the five gums studied, Semla gum produced the most stable emulsion. Dhavda and Salai are also good emulsifying agents. Arabic and Kadai gums did not produce stable emulsions when used as single substances. Addition of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants to these single individuals improved the stability coefficient values. The following orders were observed for the corresponding stability coefficient values :

Cationic

Arabic > Salai > Dhavda > Semla > Kadai

Anionic

Dhavda > Salai and Arabic (nearly equal) > Semla > Kadai

Non-ionic

Dhavda > Salai > Arabic > Semla > Kadai.

SOME very interesting work has been reported on the emulsions stabilised by surface active materials¹⁻⁴, gums^{5,6} and organic compounds^{7,8} and on properties of these emulsions^{9,10}.

In view of the medicinal importance of some gums, we have extended our previous work to study the effect of addition of surfactants along with various gums (1% suspension) on the emulsifying properties. The stability coefficient, surface tension and viscosity of the systems have been evaluated.

Experimental

The gums *Anogeissus latifolia* Wall (Bakla, Dhaura, Dhavda), *Boswellia serrata* Roxb (Luban, Salai), *Sterculia urens* (Kadai, Gulu), *Bauhinia retusa* Roxb (Semla, Kandla) were purchased from Forest Deptt. Maharashtra State, Poona. *Acacia nilotica* (Arabic, Babul) was obtained from National Botanical Garden, Lucknow.

The gums were purified by the methods described by Mukherjee and Shukla¹¹. The emulsions were prepared at 25° by the method of King and Mukherjee¹², using 1% suspension of various gums alone and then adding fixed concentration of various surface-active agents (B.D.H. A.R. quality) viz., cetyl-trimethyl ammonium-bromide (cationic), sodium lauryl sulphate (anionic) and Triton x-100 (non-ionic) keeping the ratio of kerosene oil to water as 40 : 60 so that the emulsions produced were not very viscous and could be used easily for practical purposes. The size frequency analyses were done immediately and at different intervals of time starting from the 1st day of preparation to the 8th week of ageing by the method of King and Mukherjee¹².

The stability coefficient values were computed by fitting the data into the theory of least squares as done by Mukherjee and Shukla¹¹. The surface

tension and viscosities were determined at 25° using drop weight method and Ostwald's viscometer method respectively. These data have been presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Results and Discussion

The suspension of Dhavda gum shows the highest viscosity. Its surface tension is also high but lower than that of Semla gum. Addition of 0.1% cationic, anionic and non-ionic surface-active agents to 1% suspension of the gum shows a change in viscosity from 1.014 centipoise to 1.122 centipoise. The increase is highest in the case of non-ionic surfactant triton x-100 and least in the case of anionic surfactant sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS). There was a decrease in the value of surface tension with all the surfactants. The least reduction was observed in the case of anionic surfactant while it was maximum in the case of non-ionic surfactant. Out of the five gums studied Dhavda gum suspension produced emulsions which were next to Semla stabilised emulsions. Observation of Table 2 shows that addition of surfactants resulted in appreciable enhancement of the stability coefficient values. This enhancement in the stability coefficient values can be recorded as Tx-100 > SLS > CTAB. The enhancement is apparently due to high internal viscosity of the emulsions which prevents coalescence of the particles into bigger ones.

Salai gum suspension shows a marked increase in the viscosity values on addition of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants (0.1%). The increase is in the same order as in the case of Dhavda gum but the increase is only upto 1.172 centipoise in the case of non-ionic surfactants. A similar trend in lowering of surface tension is observed on addition of surface-active agents. There is a marked increase in the stability factors on addition of surfactants and the increase is much greater

TABLE 1—DATA FOR 40% KEROSENE OIL EMULSIONS AND THE SURFACE TENSION AND VISCOSITY VALUES OF THE CORRESPONDING SUSPENSIONS OF THE STABILISERS (GUMS)

Emulsion No.	Stabiliser (Gum 1%)	Stability Coefficient Values $\times 10^3$	Graphically determined initial specific area $\times 10^3$ [cm ² /gm]	Surface tension [dynes/cm]	Viscosity [centipoise]
1.	Dhavda	10.24	4.95	67.46	1.014
2.	Salai	5.85	4.41	65.85	0.914
3.	Arabic	Broken	—	61.02	1.035
4.	Kadai	Broken	—	60.07	0.921
5.	Semla	15.19	12.90	65.88	0.948

TABLE 2—DATA FOR 40% KEROSENE OIL EMULSIONS AND THE SURFACE TENSION AND VISCOSITY VALUES OF THE CORRESPONDING SUSPENSIONS OF THE STABILISERS

Emulsion No.	Stabiliser mixture Gum(1%) + surfactant	Initial specific area $\times 10^3$ graphically determined [cm ² /gm]	Stability coefficient values $\times 10^3$	Surface Tension [dynes/cm]	Viscosity [centipoise]
1.	Dhavda + 0.1% CTAB	13.18	31.82	64.93	1.037
2.	Dhavda + 0.5% CTAB	9.22	26.05	66.04	1.004
3.	Dhavda + 0.1% SLS	13.18	34.34	66.89	1.033
4.	Dhavda + 0.05% SLS	8.91	24.48	67.12	1.018
5.	Dhavda + 0.01% Tx-100	12.16	39.78	61.08	1.122
6.	Dhavda + 0.05% Tx-100	7.41	12.83	62.74	1.087
7.	Salai + 0.1% CTAB	12.44	40.70	62.55	0.984
8.	Salai + 0.05% CTAB	8.51	20.05	63.86	0.974
9.	Salai + 0.1% SLS	9.33	34.82	65.60	1.017
10.	Salai + 0.05% SLS	9.12	16.11	65.75	0.991
11.	Salai + 0.1% Tx-100	9.22	24.67	62.28	1.172
12.	Salai + 0.05% Tx-100	9.54	9.55	64.07	1.111
13.	Arabic + 0.1% CTAB	13.03	45.44	60.39	1.068
14.	Arabic + 0.05% CTAB	9.12	25.05	60.83	1.037
15.	Arabic + 0.1% SLS	9.22	34.43	60.06	1.165
16.	Arabic + 0.05% SLS	7.16	16.87	61.00	0.974
17.	Arabic + 0.1% Tx-100	12.02	23.59	59.57	1.141
18.	Arabic + 0.05% Tx-100	7.76	15.23	60.04	1.131
19.	Kadai + 0.1% CTAB	—	broken	58.84	1.007
20.	Kadai + 0.05% CTAB	—	broken	59.26	0.943
21.	Kadai + 0.1% SLS	3.54	0.31	59.80	1.005
22.	Kadai + 0.05% SLS	—	broken	59.93	0.965
23.	Kadai + 0.1% Tx-100	7.94	1.11	57.90	1.015
24.	Kadai + 0.05% Tx-100	—	broken	60.06	0.999
25.	Semla + 0.1% CTAB	9.77	25.51	64.00	1.053
26.	Semla + 0.05% CTAB	—	broken	65.59	1.002
27.	Semla + 0.1% SLS	12.58	19.35	64.35	1.001
28.	Semla + 0.05% SLS	9.39	18.84	65.52	0.994
29.	Semla + 0.1% Tx-100	8.60	18.46	64.14	1.078
30.	Semla + 0.05% Tx-100	8.91	13.21	64.93	1.012

compared to Dhavda gum stabilised emulsions. The stability coefficient values show the order: CTAB > SLS > Tx-100.

Kadai gum suspension has got the lowest values of surface tension. Addition of different surface-active agents was least effective in reducing the surface tension as is evident from Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

It is evident from the data of Table 1 that 1% gum arabic alone is not capable of producing good and stable emulsions with kerosene oil. Addition of 0.1% cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants produced more stable emulsions, stability coefficients being 45.44, 34.43 and 23.59 respectively.

Kadai gum alone is not capable of producing emulsion as is evident from stability coefficient data of Table 1. Addition of non-ionic surfactant makes the emulsion stable but stability coefficient value in this case is only 1.11.

Out of the five substances used, Semla gum produced the most stable emulsion. Addition of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants did not improve the stability coefficient values to any great extent, as is evident from Table 2. Stable emulsions were produced only in the case of cationic surfactant.

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